

Supporting Information

Interfacial Behavior of Methane in Methane/*p*-Xylene/Water Systems: First Principles Inspected Using Neutron Imaging and Molecular Dynamics Simulations

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SI-1: Comparisons of simulated quantities to literature data

Comparison of the MD-predictions for the binary systems with the literature data is of importance, particularly in cases in which the NI data are not available. Diffusivity of water in liquid *p*-xylene and methane in liquid water (**Figure S1**), IFT, and viscosity for pure water (**Figure S2**) were predicted and compared to the available experimental data. Although discernible differences of the predictions from the reference datasets were observed, these comparisons provide an assessment of expected errors, trends, and the underlying physics were captured well. Further predictions for the binary systems are summarized in Table 1 in the main text. In **Figure S3**, predicted diffusivities in the cell reference frame (D_A , D_B), and partial molar volumes for methane and *p*-xylene, including the viscosity correction adjusted based on the NI results, are shown. Such data pertinently complement the observables shown in Figure 2a, 2c in the main text, while they remain hardly accessible experimentally.

Figure S1. Simulated diffusivity of water (C) in an infinitely diluted solution of *p*-xylene in water (a), simulated diffusivity of methane (A) in a saturated solution of methane in water at 1 bar of methane (b). Points are simulated (a) and experimental (b) data, curves indicate regressions of simulated data (see Table 1) and experimental data from the literature: # ^[1], ## ^[2].

Figure S2. IFT (a) and viscosity (b) of water at saturated vapor pressure. Simulated data are compared to the literature # ^[3].

Figure S3. MD simulated diffusivity of methane and *p*-xylene in their binary liquid solution corresponding to the indicated methane pressure [$T \in (283 \text{ K}, 353 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.23)$] with $k_\eta = 0.872$ adjusted based on the comparison of NI and MD simulation. Curves are regressions of simulated data listed in the SD.

SI-2: Role of *p*-xylene polarity on *p*-xylene/water interfacial tension and affinity of methane

The energy of the water/*p*-xylene interface, i.e., interfacial tension (IFT), is directly evaluated from the equilibrium simulation of a two-phase system utilizing the pressure tensor. To validate our model for water/*p*-xylene interface, we aim to reproduce not only the absolute value of IFT but also its temperature dependence (see left and right panels of **Figure S4**). We relied on TIP4P/2005 water model, which reproduces well water structure, thermodynamics, and phase behavior. For *p*-xylene, united-atom TraPPE FF was used at first (for consistency with our earlier work ^[4]). However, we have observed that the IFT is too large ($\sim 56 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ at 298 K) while the temperature dependence ^[5] is in fair agreement with experimental data for the water/benzene system [$\sim -0.1 \text{ mN m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$]. In contrast, the all-atom representation of *p*-xylene (see MD Methods) resulted in a reasonable IFT of $\sim 30 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ at 298 K, but the sensitivity to temperature changes was completely lost.

The major difference between the two parameterizations is that in TraPPE FF all beads carry zero partial charge, while in the all-atom representation, the partial charges on carbon and hydrogen atoms are on the order of few tenths of an elementary charge (see Table S1).

We note that all *p*-xylene models phase separate with water, i.e., within numerical accuracy of our calculations water and *p*-xylene are virtually immiscible (**Figure S5**). On the quantitative level, the interface is sharper for completely uncharged *p*-xylene, and the mutual penetration to the subsurface of the other phase is the largest when full partial charges on *p*-xylene are employed. If we quantify the width of the interface by the region where normalized density increases from 0.1 to 0.9, the width of the interface rises from 0.4 nm (uncharged *p*-xylene) to 0.6 nm (full partial charges on *p*-xylene).

Further, methane interactions are not directly affected by *p*-xylene parameterization, since methane is treated at the united-atom level as a single uncharged LJ sphere, i.e., methane is not involved in electrostatic interactions.

Figure S6 summarizes the propensity of methane to the water/*p*-xylene interface at $T = 283 \text{ K}$ in terms of particle density profiles (left panels) and normalized density profiles (right panel). The *p*-xylene/water interface is always located at $z = 0$, with *p*-xylene phase on the left (dashed lines) and water phase on the right (dotted lines, divided by 10). The top panel (Figure S6a) illustrates the role of *p*-xylene parameterization (see the legend) on interfacial affinity of methane (full lines) at fixed concentration, $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.15$. Methane is enriched at the interface if

p-xylene is fully uncharged (black line), surface neutral at ca half of the full charges, and depleted from the interface at full partial charges on *p*-xylene.

The evolution of the partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase are shown for the uncharged *p*-xylene in the middle row (Figure S6b), and for the full partial charges on *p*-xylene in the bottom row (Figure S6c). We hypothesize that at full partial charges on *p*-xylene, the interface is still a liquid mixture containing water, which prohibits the presence of methane molecules. If the *p*-xylene charges are low, the interfacial water is more disordered (more like vapor phase water), allowing methane to enter the interfacial region. Another argument is based on the total mass density profile, right panel of Figure S5.

The surface excess/depletion of methane at different methane concentrations and for different partial charges of *p*-xylene determined from density profiles in Figure S6 is shown on the left axis of **Figure S7** and recalculated to change in IFT (right axis). Although the interfacial activity of methane qualitatively changes with *p*-xylene parameterization, the quantitative effect of methane on IFT is marginal $\pm 1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ at the highest methane contents ($x_{\text{Me}} \approx 0.3$).

The noticeable dip in total density in the *p*-xylene subsurface region (ca 0.3 nm thick), may allow for localization of methane in that region (compare Figure S5 and S6, focusing on zero charge FF). Assuming the decrease in density is $\approx 50 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, it accounts for $\approx 6 \%$ of total mass density (850 kg m^{-3}), in other words there is $\approx 6 \%$ free subsurface volume available for methane. This is $0.06 \times (1 \text{ nm} \times 1 \text{ nm} \times 0.3 \text{ nm}) = 0.018 \text{ nm}^3$ free volume per 1 nm^2 of liquid/liquid interface. For a methane particle ($V_A^{\text{app}} = 0.075 \text{ nm}^3/\text{particle}$) this volume allows to accommodate only $\approx 0.25 \text{ particle/nm}^2$, which is on the scale with the methane surface excess observed in Figure S7.

Figure S4. Comparison of the temperature dependence of IFT for water/*p*-xylene for series of all-atom *p*-xylene parameterizations, where the partial charges are globally scaled by the scaling factor (1 = partial charges of the original FF, 0 = zero partial charges) as indicated by the legend. The relative changes with temperature are compared in the left panel; the absolute values are compared in the right panel. Simulations were compared at external pressure $p = 50$ bar.

Figure S5. Left panel presents the comparison of the shapes of normalized partial density profiles of water (full lines) and *p*-xylene (dashed lines) in the vicinity of water/*p*-xylene interface for a series of partial charges on *p*-xylene molecule (see the legend and Table S1, 1 = partial charges of the original FF, 0 = zero partial charges) at $T = 283$ K. The Gibbs dividing surface is, for convenience, located at $z_{\text{GDS}} = 0$. The sharpening of the interface with reducing

partial charges on *p*-xylene (thus promoting its nonpolar character) is clearly documented. The total mass density close to the interface is shown in the right panel.

Figure S6. Overview of methane affinity (partial density profile) to the water/*p*-xylene interface at $T = 283$ K. Partial densities of methane (full line), water (dotted line, divided by 10), and *p*-xylene (dashed line). Top row (a), variation of methane affinity with reducing partial charges (see Table S1) on *p*-xylene molecule at selected concentration of methane ($x_{\text{Me}} = 0.15$) in *p*-xylene phase. Middle row (b), results for *p*-xylene with zero partial charges, evolution of partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase. Bottom row (c), results for *p*-xylene with original partial charges, evolution of partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase.

Figure S7. Role of partial charges in *p*-xylene molecule (see the legend, 1 means partial charges of the original FF, 0 means zero partial charges) on the excess of methane at water/*p*-xylene interface (left axis) and on IFT (right axis). Data are shown at $T = 283$ K and external pressure $p = 50$ bar.

Table S1. Parameterization of the *p*-xylene molecule, including its name, mass, Lennard-Jones parameters, and partial charges. Partial charges vary from Full ($s = 1.0$) to Zero ($s = 0$), as is used in simulations, which are discussed in this section. The molecular structure of *p*-xylene with atom names is attached for clarity ^{a)}.

Atom name	Mass [a.u.]	σ [nm]	ϵ [kJ mol ⁻¹]	Full ($s = 1.0$) [e]	$s = 0.9$ [e]	$s = 0.75$ [e]	$s = 0.5$ [e]	$s = 0.25$ [e]	Zero ($s = 0$) [e]
C00	12.01	0.350	0.276	-0.2	-0.17	-0.14	-0.1	-0.05	0
C01	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.09	-0.08	-0.06	-0.04	-0.02	0
C02	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
C03	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
C04	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.09	-0.08	-0.06	-0.04	-0.02	0
C05	12.01	0.350	0.276	-0.2	-0.17	-0.14	-0.1	-0.05	0
C06	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
C07	12.01	0.355	0.293	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
H08	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0

H09	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
H0A	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
H0B	1.01	0.242	0.126	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
H0C	1.01	0.242	0.126	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
H0D	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
H0E	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
H0F	1.01	0.250	0.126	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
H0G	1.01	0.242	0.126	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
H0H	1.01	0.242	0.126	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0

a)

SI-3: Illustration of the equivalence between surface excess and change in IFT – water/methane

On an example of IFT of water in the presence of methane gas, we demonstrate two equivalent evaluations of IFT from the MD simulation data. The macroscopic route utilizes the pressure tensor, while the microscopic route employs the structural data, such as methane surface excess and non-ideality in the gas phase.

Figure S8 presents a series of partial density profiles of methane across the water/methane interface. Defining the Gibbs dividing surface (based on water density profile), surface excess of methane (Γ_{21}) is calculated. This allows us to evaluate the change in IFT (**Figure S9**). These results are compared to values of IFT determined directly from the pressure tensor, see Figure S9d.

Figure S8. Partial density profiles of methane (full lines) and water (dashed lines) across the water/methane interface at 298 K and a series of methane pressures (see the legend). The left panel presents the number densities (note that water density is divided by 10 to be on the same scale). The densities in the right panel are normalized to their bulk values in order to easily compare the relative surface excess under different methane pressures.

Figure S9. Comparison of the change in IFT of water in contact with methane gas (p_{Me} ranges from 10 to 100 bar) as determined directly from the pressure tensor and indirectly from density profiles and surface excess.

Panel a (top left) presents the surface excess of methane and a nonlinear (Langmuir-like) fit. The surface excess data were evaluated from density profiles, such as in Figure S8.

Panel b (top right) presents methane concentration normalized surface excess (full lines) and this term multiplied by methane nonideality correction (dashed lines).

Panel c (bottom left) presents the integral of the ($-1\times$) integrand shown in **Panel b**, which equals to the change in IFT in $k_B T$ units.

Panel d (bottom left) evaluated changes in IFT, with (dashed lines) and without (full lines) the methane gas nonideality correction. These results are compared to data (points), which present changes of IFT directly calculated from the pressure tensor. The full lines are shown only for the lowest (black) and the highest (gray) temperature for clarity.

Figure S10. Fugacity coefficient (ϕ) of methane in the range of investigated methane densities in the gas phase (i.e., methane pressures in the range 10–100 bar) and temperatures (283–353 K, see the legend). Data at the lowest pressures are scattered due to relatively large pressure fluctuations and were not used in linear fits of the data. The inset shows the temperature dependence of 2nd virial coefficient B_2 . These fugacity coefficients were used in $\Delta\gamma$ calculations in Figure S9.

SI-4: Surface excess and change in IFT for *p*-xylene/methane

Applying the protocol from SI-2 on the *p*-xylene/methane interface, we connect the methane surface excess with the *p*-xylene IFT and compare it with the direct results obtained from the pressure tensor. For clarity reasons, we present results only at standard temperature $T = 298$ K. We confirmed the experimental observation that although methane is quite soluble in *p*-xylene ($H \approx 400$ bar), it is surface active. It is noteworthy that the IFT suppression (i.e., surface activity) by methane is larger for *p*-xylene than for water at the same methane pressures (i.e., methane density in the gas phase). Methane nonideality in the gas phase is accounted for by the methane fugacity coefficient ϕ , as shown in **Figure S10**.

Figure S11 presents a series of partial density profiles of methane across the *p*-xylene/methane interface. Defining the Gibbs dividing surface (based on *p*-xylene density profile), surface excess of methane (Γ_{21}) is calculated. An example of the surface excess evaluation is shown in

Figure S15. This allows us to evaluate the change in IFT (**Figure S12**). These results are compared to values of IFT determined directly from the pressure tensor (Figure S12d).

Figure S11. Partial density profiles of methane (full lines) and *p*-xylene (dashed lines) across the *p*-xylene/methane interface at 298 K and a series of methane pressures (see the legend). The left panel presents the number densities. The densities in the right panel are normalized to their bulk values in order to easily compare the relative surface excess under different methane pressures.

Figure S12. Comparison of the change in IFT of *p*-xylene in contact with methane gas (p_{Me} from 10 to 100 bar, i.e., ρ_{Me} from 0.26 to 2.8 nm^{-3}), as determined directly from pressure tensor and indirectly from density profiles and surface excess.

Panel a (top left) presents the surface excess (Γ_{21}) of methane and a nonlinear (Langmuir-like) fit. The surface excess data were evaluated from density profiles, such as in Figure S11.

Panel b (top right) presents methane concentration normalized surface excess (full lines) and this term multiplied by methane nonideality (dashed lines).

Panel c (bottom left) presents the integral of the $(-1 \times)$ integrand shown in **Panel b**, which equals to the change in IFT in $k_{\text{B}}T$ units.

Panel d (bottom left) evaluated changes in IFT, with (dashed lines) and without (full lines) the methane gas nonideality correction. These results are compared to data (points), which present changes of IFT directly calculated from the pressure tensor.

SI-5: Determination of macroscopic properties of a poorly soluble component

When macroscopic properties of a poorly soluble component (e.g., diffusion, partial molar volumes, volume fractions) should be evaluated from bulk MD simulations, it is important to assure that homogeneous phases are simulated. The extensive presence of associates (either permanent or transient) would cause erroneous determination of macroscopic properties from simulation data. For solutions that contain small molecules, the convenient indicator of self-association is the radial distribution function (RDF), which tailing indicates the formation of larger structures. For a series of concentrations, RDFs of poorly soluble molecules were calculated. The results are summarized in Figure S11.

Figure S13a (left) presents methane dissolved in water. It was found that up to $x_{\text{Me}} \approx 2$ mol.% (i.e., $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 600$ bar as $H \approx 30\,000$ bar), methane behaves as a well-dissolved gas. However, when a sufficient number of molecules is available, transient and at higher concentration, even permanent methane nanobubbles are formed. The indication is a high peak and broad shoulder in RDF at $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.1$ (i.e., 250 methane molecules in the simulation box).

Figure S13b (middle) presents *p*-xylene dissolved in water, where a similar situation applies. *p*-xylene forms associates when a sufficient number of *p*-xylene molecules are available to form a hydrophobic core. In our simulation setup, the high peak and broad shoulder in RDF are observed already at $x_{\text{pXY}} = 0.02$ (50 *p*-xylene molecules in the simulation box).

Figure S13c (right) presents water dissolved in *p*-xylene. In this system, even at the lowest, but finite concentration of water ($x_{\text{water}} = 0.01$, 5 water molecules in the simulation box), water molecules strongly interact with each other (via H-bond networks) and form stable associates (identified by high peak in water-water RDF ≈ 200 , compared to ≈ 4 in pure water). The diffusion coefficient would be proportional to the droplet size. Therefore, to gather sufficient statistics for this system, we used extensive sampling (10 x 100 ns) of a single water molecule in *p*-xylene phase (i.e., infinite dilution approach).

Figure S13. Radial distribution functions (RDF) for poorly miscible molecules in given solvents. Tailing in RDFs indicates a self-association and formation of large-sized objects, providing the threshold for determination of conditions of stable homogeneous systems. The left panel presents methane-methane self-association in water, the middle panel *p*-xylene-*p*-xylene self-association in water, and the right panel water-water self-association in *p*-xylene. We note that for water as solvent 1 mol.% means 25 molecules, while for *p*-xylene as solvent 1 mol.% means 5 molecules in the simulation box.

SI-6: Density profiles of studied interfaces

Figure S14. Normalized z-density profiles of methane (black), *p*-xylene (red), and water (blue) in the vicinity of interfaces of the studied systems. *p*-xylene/methane(gas) is in full line, water/methane(gas) is in dashed line. *p*-xylene with dissolved methane/water is in dot-dashed for zero partial charges on *p*-xylene and double-dot-dash for full partial charges on *p*-xylene. All systems correspond to an equilibrium methane pressure $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 50$ bar. The middle panel presents the changes in shape of *p*-xylene interface (overlying its Gibbs dividing surface), when in contact with gas or with the other liquid, the lower panel presents the data from perspective of water interface. Note that water interface keeps closely its width, while *p*-xylene is significantly narrower (and sharper) when in contact with water phase.

The densities of water and *p*-xylene are normalized to their bulk values, that of methane is normalized to the density in the gas phase (directly shown for *p*-xylene/methane and water/methane, and indirectly applied for *p*-xylene with dissolved methane/water. This representation simplifies the comparison of the relative surface excess of methane in different systems, as well as the comparison of structures at the interface.

SI-7: Illustration of surface excess - *p*-xylene/methane

Figure S15. Normalized *z*-density profiles of methane (red), *p*-xylene (black) in the vicinity of the *p*-xylene/methane(gas) interface at $T = 298$ K and $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 100$ bar (i.e., $\rho_{\text{Me}} \approx 2.8 \text{ nm}^{-3}$). Gibbs dividing surface (GDS) is located at $z = 0$ and the red area under the methane curve defines the surface excess (Γ) on the side of the *p*-xylene phase ($z < 0$) and on the methane gas phase ($z > 0$). The running integral of surface excess is shown in green.

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